

Original article

Survey of Wild Trees and Shrubs in Eastern Region of Libya and Their Economical Value

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the present study was to identify the wild trees and shrubs among the diverse flora of Eastern region ecosystem that are used economically and therapeutically. Current data revealed that the total number of wild trees and shrubs surveyed in the region was 88 species, belonging to 31 families and 62 genera. *Retama monosperma* (L.) Boiss. subsp. *bovei* (Spach) Maire has been collected for the first time and it forms a new record for Libya, with the presence of three endemic taxa *Arbutus pavarii* Pamp., *Cupressus sempervirens* L. var. *horizontalis* (Mill.) Gordon. and *Capparis spinosa* var. *krugeriana*. The species collected were traditionally used for medicinal and non-medicinal purposes. More than 80 medicinal uses were recorded for 46 species mentioned in the present study and 10 non-medicinal uses were also mentioned

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INTRODUCTION

Libya is considered rich in arboreal species which are used in many uses, especially Cyrenaica (Aljabal Akhder region), which contains most of the total arboreal species recorded in Libya [1]. The Green Mountains (Aljabal Akhder) were considered to be one of the most important topographical phenomena in Libya [2], which also included desert, wadis and prairies. Al-Idrissi reported that the main forest type in Libya was found to be the natural forest occurring in Gebel Akhder region [3]. The total area of the forest was about 500,000 hectares, of which 35% has been converted to agriculture. Thus, the actual area of these natural forests is now about 32,000 hectares. The same authors studied plant genetic resources in Libya, and found an imminent danger of genetic erosion of all wild species, especially in Gebel Akhder, because of the heavy grazing, human use and drought hazards which occur more frequently in the country. The vegetation of Libya is studied by Ranck, he noted that the Cyrenaica plateau consisted of a variety of arborescent species, grasses and other herbaceous plants [4]. Most of the canyons and broad slopes of the plateau were covered with dense chaparral consisting of several genera of tree like forms. These genera included primarily *Quercus*, *Viburnum* and *Juniperus*. Some of the larger wadis, such as Wadi El-Kuf, supported occasional stands of *Pinus* and *Cupressus* [5]. Additionally, Johnson in his publication Jabal al-Akhder, Cyrenaica, reported that the steppe was formed of a number of separate communities [6]. The first band of the steppe was dominated by Mediterranean biota characterized by such species as *Ziziphus lotus*, and *Sacropoterium spinosum*. Asker noted that the vegetation of Gebel Akhder is characterized by Maquis [7]. It largely consists of open scrub, with thickets of tall shrub and small trees. It is a jumble of *Arbutus pavarii*, *Ceratonia siliqua*, *Juniperus phoenicea*, *Olea europaea*, *Viburnum tinus*, *Quercus coccifera* and *Rhus tripartita*. Johnson in his study on the vegetation of Gebel Akhder noted that the Bedouins recognized that numerous plants are valuable for their medicinal properties [6]. Among these was *Rosmarinus officinalis*, *Thymus capitatus* and *Arbutus pavarii*.

Boulos, mentioned that Aljabal Akhder is considered the richest area in vegetation with the highest number of species were about 50% of the total plant species of the Libyan flora are confined to this region [8,9]. Recently, there is an imminent danger of genetic erosion of the vegetation in Eastern region because of heavy grazing, collection of medicinal and woody plants for local use and trading, over cultivation, recurrent drought conditions and hazards [10].

Studies available regarding the economic and medicinal importance of wild trees and shrubs in Libya are very rare. The main objective of the present work is to collect and identify the wild trees and shrubs among the diverse flora of Eastern region of Libya ecosystem that are used economically and therapeutically. These will provide valuable information for the future conservation and management strategies of these natural resources in Libya.

METHODS

Subjects

Data and specimens of the wild trees and shrubs in Libya were collected during field trips between 2012 and 2016. Field work consisted of two phases: 1) collecting and studying the trees and shrubs in Eastern region of Libya and 2) interviews with local inhabitants, herbalists and practitioners. Open-ended questionnaires [11] were applied separately for each informant to achieve the second point. The total numbers of interviewed informants were 49 men (more than 50 years old). Specific questions focused on the different ethnobotanical uses traditionally practiced in the area (e.g. food, medicine, construction, fixation of sand dunes, fuel wood, tanning, dying, handicrafts, fodder etc.) were asked for the interviewees. Nevertheless, details for the different medicinal uses were also considered.

Plant specimens were collected during flowering and fruiting stages as much as possible. The date of collection, habitat type, vernacular name, flower colour, locality. Photographs of a large number of plants were taken in their natural habitats. The identification of the specimens was carried out according to the Flora of Libya [12-1]. Wherever possible, identification was confirmed by comparing with the authentically identified specimens in the herbarium. The voucher specimens have been deposited in the Kelieda Herbarium, Botany Department, Alqubba, Omar El-Mukhtar University.

RESULTS

From the study area, 88 species were collected belonging to 62 genera and 31 families. Gymnosperms are represented by 3 families including 4 genera and 6 species. Angiosperms include 82 plant species belonging to 28 families and 58 genera (Table 1). The largest family is Chenopodiaceae which is represented by 19 species and 10 genera followed by Fabaceae (Leguminosae) with 10 species. The largest genera are *Atripelx* and *Salsola*, which includes 4 species. *Retama monosperma* (L.) Boiss. subsp. *bovei* (Spach) Maire has been collected for the first time and it forms a new record for Libya, with the presence of three endemic taxa *Arbutus pavarii* Pamp., *Cupressus sempervirens* L. var. *Horizontalis* (Mill.) Gordon and *Capparis spinosa* var. *krugeriana*. The woody species in study area are rich and varied from Mediterranean, desert and salt marshes species.

Table 1. A complete list of the wild trees and shrubs collected from Eastern region of Libya.

Scientific Name	Local Name	Family
<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Delile. subs. <i>astringens</i> (Schum. & Thoun.) Roberty	Sant	Fabaceae
<i>Alhagi graecorum</i> Boiss.	Agol	Fabaceae
<i>Anabasis articulata</i> (Forssk.) Moq.	Agram	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Anagyris foetida</i> L.	Kharroub El-Klab	Fabaceae
<i>Arbutus pavarii</i> Pamp.	Shmary	Ericaceae
<i>Arthrocnemum fruticosum</i> (L.) Moq.	Ghetham	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Arthrocnemum macrostachyum</i> (Moris) Moris	Balbal jemaal	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Arthrocnemum perenne</i> (Mill.) Moss.	Zeetah	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Atripelx coriacea</i> Forssk.	Qataf	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Atripelx halimus</i> L.	Qataf	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Atripelx mollis</i> Desf.	Qataf -Zell	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Atripelx stylosa</i> Viv.	Qataf	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Ballota pseudo-dictamnus</i> (L.) Benth.	Mayla	Lamiaceae
<i>Calicotome spinosa</i> (L.) Link	Gandol	Fabaceae
<i>Calicotome villosa</i> (Poiret) Link	Gandol	Fabaceae
<i>Capparis spinosa</i> L.	Kabbar	Capparaceae

<i>Ceratonia siliqua</i> L.	Kharroub	Fabaceae
<i>Cistus incans</i> L.	Birbish	Cistaceae
<i>Cistus parviflorus</i> Lam.	Birbish	Cistaceae
<i>Cistus salvifolius</i> L.	Birbish	Cistaceae
<i>Clematis cirrhosa</i> L.	Clematish	Ranunculaceae
<i>Cornulaca monacantha</i> Del.	Hadd	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i> L. var. <i>horizontalis</i> (Mill.) Gordon	Srow – Qiliz	Cupressaceae
<i>Ephedera alata</i> Decne.	Alendi	Ephederaceae
<i>Ephedera altissima</i> Desf.	Alendi	Ephederaceae
<i>Erica multiflora</i> L.	Hamraya	Ericaceae
<i>Erica sicula</i> Guss.	Hamra	Ericaceae
<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i> L.	Halablab	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Farsetia aegyptia</i> Turra	Farsetia	Brassicaceae
<i>Genista acanthoclada</i> DC.	Lihyat Alsheikh	Fabaceae
<i>Halimione portulacoides</i> (L.) Allen	Halimon	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Halocnemum strobilaceum</i> (Pall.) M. Bieb.	Shenin	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Halogeton alopecuroides</i> (Delile) Moq.	Tashash	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Haloxylon scoparium</i> Pomel	Rimth	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Juniperus oxycedrus</i> L.	Arar Suky	Cupressaceae
<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i> L.	Shaara - Arar	Cupressaceae
<i>Laurus nobilis</i> L.	Ghar - Rand	Lauraceae
<i>Limoniastrum monopetalum</i> (L.) Boiss	Zaita	Plumbaginaceae
<i>Lonicera etrusca</i> Santi	Jummet Fata	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Lonicera nummularifolia</i> Santi	Jummet Fata	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Lycium europaeum</i> L.	Awsaj	Solanaceae
<i>Lycium schweinfurthii</i> Dammer	Awsaj	Solanaceae
<i>Lycium shawii</i> Roemer & Schultes	Awsaj	Solanaceae
<i>Myrtus communis</i> L.	Mersin.	Myrtaceae
<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Defla	Apocynaceae
<i>Nicotiana glauca</i> R.C.Graham	Akkuz Musa	Solanaceae
<i>Nitraria retusa</i> L.	Ghardaq	Nitrariaceae
<i>Olea europaea</i> L. subs. <i>europaea</i> var. <i>sylvestris</i> (Mill.) Lehr	Zaitoun	Oleaceae
<i>Opuntia ficus-indica</i> (L.) Mill.	Hindi	Cactaceae
<i>Pergularia tomentosa</i> L.	Tham Nesser	Asclepiadaceae
<i>Periploca angustifolia</i> Labill.	Helaab	Asclepiadaceae
<i>Philyrea angustifolia</i> L.	Sakhab	Oleaceae
<i>Philyrea latifolia</i> L.	Sakhab	Oleaceae
<i>Phlomis floccosa</i> D. Don.	Zeheira	Lamiaceae
<i>Pinus halepensis</i> Mill.	Senouber	Pinaceae
<i>Pistachia atlantica</i> Desf.	Battoum	Anacardiaceae
<i>Pistachia lentiscus</i> L.	Battoum	Anacardiaceae
<i>Prasium majus</i> L.	Anab eddib	Lamiaceae
<i>Quercus coccifera</i> L.	Ballout	Fagaceae
<i>Retama monosperma</i> (L.) Boiss. subsp. <i>bovei</i> (Spach) Maire	Ratam	Fabaceae

<i>Retama raetam</i> (Forssk.) Weeb& Berthel.	Ratam	Fabaceae
<i>Rhamnus alaternus</i> L subsp. <i>pendulus</i> (Pamp.) Jafri.	Sellouf	Rhamnaceae
<i>Rhamnus lycioides</i> L.	Sellouf	Rhamnaceae
<i>Rhamnus oleoides</i> L.	Sellouf	Rhamnaceae
<i>Rhus tripartita</i> (Ucria) Grande	Gdari	Anacardiaceae
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Kherwa	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> L.	Iklil	Lamiaceae
<i>Rubus sanctus</i> Schreb.	Olleiq	Rosaceae
<i>Sacropoterium spinosum</i> (L.) Spach	Shobroq	Rosaceae
<i>Salix subserrata</i> Willd.	Safsaaaf	Salicaceae
<i>Salsola baryosma</i> (Roem.& Schult.) Dandy	Ressal - Talizza	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Salsola longifolia</i> Forssk.	Shadida	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Salsola tetrandra</i> Forssk.	Gel - Feres	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Salsola tetragona</i> Delile	Gel	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Smilax aspera</i> L.	Rough	Smilacaceae
<i>Spartium junceum</i> L.	El-Wazal	Fabaceae
<i>Suaeda vera</i> Forssk. ex J.F.Gmel.	Sabta	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Suaeda vermiculata</i> Forssk.	Sabta	Chenopodiaceae
<i>Tamarix aphylla</i> L.	Athel	Tamaricaceae
<i>Tamarix nilotica</i> (Ehrenb.) Bunge.	Tarfa	Tamaricaceae
<i>Teucrium brevifolium</i> Schreber	Jaada	Lamiaceae
<i>Thymelea hirsuta</i> (L.) Endl.	Mithnan	Thymelaeaceae
<i>Viburnum tinus</i> L.	Mernakh	Caprifoliaceae
<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal	Foul El-Kelab	Solanaceae
<i>Ziziphus lotus</i> (L.) Lam.	Sidr -Nabq	Rhamnaceae
<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i> (L.) Willd.	Sidr -Nabq	Rhamnaceae
<i>Zygophyllum album</i> L.	Balbal - Rotreit	Zygophyllaceae
<i>Zygophyllum geslinii</i> Coss.	Balbal	Zygophyllaceae

Data in Table 2 indicated that 46 species were used for medicinal purposes, 12 species as food, 14 species for honey production, 14 species as fodder, 16 species as ornament, and 25 species for industry. On the other hand, one may notice that same species may have more than one purpose (e.g., *Arbutus pavarii* for medicine, honey production, food, industry and in construction; *Rosmarinus officinalis* for medicine, honey production and ornament; *Ceratonia siliqua* for medicine, honey production, food, industry, fodder and in construction and *Ziziphus lotus* for medicine, honey production and food). It is interesting to note that more than 20 species out of 88 were not mentioned by the informants to have any economic value.

Table 2: The economic value of the trees and shrubs in Eastern region of Libya.

Economic Parameter	Species
1. Medicinal uses	<i>Anagyris foetida, Arbutus pavarii, Atriplex halimus, Ballota pseudodictamnus, Calicotome villosa, Capparis spinosa, Ceratonia siliqua, Cistus parviflorus, Cistus salvifolius, Cupressus sempervirens, Ephedera alata, Ephedera altissima, Euphorbia dendroides, Haloxylon scoparium, Juniperus phoenicea, Laurus nobilis, Lonicera etrusca, Lycium europaeum, Myrtus communis, Nerium oleander, Nicotiana glauca, Nitraria retusa, Olea europaea, Periploca angustifolia, Phillyrea angustifolia, Phlomis floccose, Pinus halepensis, Pistachia lentiscus, Quercus coccifera, Retama raetam, Rhamnus lycioides,</i>

	<i>Rhus tripartita, Ricinus communis, Rosmarinus officinalis, Rubus sanctus, Sacropoterium spinosum, Salix subserrata, Smilax aspera, Spartium junceum, Suaeda vera, Tamarix arborea, Thymelaea hirsuta, Viburnum tinus, Withania somnifera, Ziziphus lotus, Zygophyllum album</i>
2. Food	<i>Arbutus pavarii, Capparis spinosa, Ceratonia siliqua, Juniperus phoenicea, Myrtus communis, Nicotiana glauca, Nitraria retusa, Olea europaea, Opuntia ficus-indica, Pistachia lentiscus, Ziziphus lotus, Rhus tripartita.</i>
3. Honey production	<i>Arbutus pavarii (Hanon), Ballota pseudodictamnus (Maila), Capparis spinosa (Rebeh), Ceratonia siliqua (Shbro), Cistus parviflorus (Rebeh), Cistus salvifolius (Rebeh), Juniperus phoenicea (Rebeh), Myrtus communis (Rebeh), Pinus halepensis (Rebeh), Phlomis floccosa (Rebeh), Rosmarinus officinalis (Eklil), Spartium junceum (Rebeh), Viburnum tinus (Rebeh), Ziziphus lotus (Seder)</i>
4. Fodder	<i>Agathophora alopecuroides, Atripelx mollis, Atripelx stylosa, Ceratonia siliqua, Halocnemum strobilaceum, Haloxylon scoparium, Olea europaea, Opuntia ficus-indica, Periploca angustifolia, Quercus coccifera, Retama raetam, Salsola tetrandra, Ziziphus lotus, Ziziphus spina-christi.</i>
5. Ornaments	<i>Arbutus pavarii, Calicotome villosa, Capparis spinosa, Ceratonia siliqua, Cistus parviflorus, Cistus salvifolius, Lonicera etrusca, Myrtus communis, Nerium oleander, Pinus halepensis, Pistachia lentiscus, Ricinus communis, Rosmarinus officinalis, Salix subserrata, Spartium junceum, Viburnum tinus.</i>
6. Construction	<i>Arbutus pavarii, Ceratonia siliqua, Cupressus sempervirens, Pinus halepensis, Olea europaea, Laurus nobilis, Quercus coccifera, Tamarix arborea.</i>
7. Dune stabilizer	<i>Nitraria retusa, Retama raetam, Ricinus communis, Tamarix aphylla, Thymelaea hirsuta.</i>
8. Industry	<i>Acacia nilotica, Arbutus pavarii, Juniperus phoenicea, Pistachia lentiscus, Rhus tripartita, Quercus coccifera (tanning), Cupressus sempervirens, Myrtus communis, Olea europaea, Ricinus communis, Rosmarinus officinalis, Laurus nobilis, Pistachia lentiscus, Laurus nobilis, Rosmarinus officinalis (spices), Acacia nilotica, Ceratonia siliqua (juice), Laurus nobilis, Pistachia lentiscus (soap making), Pistachia lentiscus, Pistachia atlantica (resin mastic), Thymelaea hirsuta, (rope making), Myrtus communis (perfume), Pistachia atlantica, Nerium oleander (insecticides).</i>
9. Stock	<i>Olea europaea, Pistachia atlantica.</i>
10. Charcoal	<i>Laurus nobilis, Tamarix arborea, Juniperus phoenicea, Arbutus pavarii.</i>
11. Wind breaking and Hedging purposes	<i>Atripelx halimus, Cupressus sempervirens, Opuntia ficus-indica, Pinus halepensis, Tamarix aphylla.</i>

Specifically, the trees and shrubs with the medicinal value are used to treat a considerable number of ailments (Table 3). Such ailments include those of the skin (e.g. *Anagyris foetida, Cistus salvifolius, Nerium oleander, Nitraria retusa, Quercus coccifera* and *Smilax aspera*), diabetes (e.g. *Balanitis aegyptiaca, Myrtus communis, Zygophyllum album*), and to treat general and specific problems associated with the respiratory (e.g. *Cupressus sempervirens, Ephedera alata, Ephedera altissima, Myrtus communis, Pinus halepensis*), circulatory (e.g. *Cupressus sempervirens, Phillyrea angustifolia, Quercus coccifera, Rosmarinus officinalis, Zygophyllum album*), digestive (e.g. *Arbutus pavarii, Ballota pseudodictamnus, Capparis spinosa, Ceratonia siliqua, Cistus parviflorus, Cistus salvifolius, Euphorbia dendroides, Haloxylon scoparium, Juniperus phoenicea, Laurus nobilis, Ricinus communis, Viburnum tinus, Ziziphus lotus*) and reproductive system (e.g. *Ceratonia siliqua, Myrtus communis, Quercus coccifera, Rhus tripartita*). Some species are used to treat common ailments (e.g. cold, fever, flatulence and vermicide) while, others are only occasionally used to treat specific and unusual ailment such as those used for treating cancer (e.g. *Capparis spinosa, Lonicera etrusca*). Generally, the method of administration and parts used differed with the species and disease.

Table 3: A list of the medicinal trees and shrubs with its parts used and treated diseases surveyed in Eastern region of Libya.

Species	Part (s) used	Treated diseases
<i>Anagyris foetida</i>	Leaves	Dermatitis, Eczema.
<i>Arbutus pavarii</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Gastritis, Vermicide, Laxative, Urinary tract infection, Epigastritis, Renal colic, Constipation.
<i>Atriplex halimus</i>	Shoots	Chloasma.
<i>Ballota pseudodictamnus</i>	Leaves	Gastritis, Hair parasite, Urinary tract infection, Colitis.
<i>Calicotome villosa</i>	Roots, Flowers	Piles, Fistula, Epigastritis.
<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	Leaves, Flowers	Diuretic, Sciatica, Wounds, Diabetes, Gastritis, Rheumatic, Sun stroke, Womb and stomach tumors.
<i>Ceratonia siliqua</i>	Legume, Leaves, Seeds	Acidity, Indigestion, Constipation, Dyspepsia, Diuretic, Laxative, Sterility.
<i>Cistus parviflorus</i>	Leaves	Urinary tract infection, Epigastric, Gastritis.
<i>Cistus salvifolius</i>	Leaves	Gastritis, Epigastric, Eczema, Vermicide.
<i>Cupressus sempervirens</i>	Leaves, Cones	Asthma, Respiration straits, Piles, Gingivitis, Toothache, Varicose veins.
<i>Ephedera alata</i>	Shoots	Asthma, Influenza, Sinusitis, Chest allergy, Expectorant.
<i>Ephedera altissima</i>	Shoots	Asthma, Chest allergy.
<i>Euphorbia dendroides</i>	Shoots, Leaves	Gastritis, Constipation, Wounds, Herpes, Warts.
<i>Haloxylon scoparium</i>	Shoots	Epigastritis.
<i>Juniperus phoenicea</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Gastritis, Oxytotic, Vermicide, Cystitis, Ulcer, Flatulence, Colic, Colitis.
<i>Laurus nobilis</i>	Leaves	Rheumatic, Indigestion.
<i>Lonicera etrusca</i>	Leaves	Anticancer.
<i>Lycium europaeum</i>	Roots	Rheumatic, Constipation, Wounds, Dermatitis.
<i>Myrtus communis</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Diabetes, Gingivitis, Rheumatic, Common cold, Acne, Liver diseases, Ozostomia, Respiratory inflammation, Gastritis, Vaginitis.
<i>Nerium oleander</i>	Leaves	Psoriasis, Eczema, Abscess, Dermatitis, Acne.
<i>Nicotiana glauca</i>	Leaves	Hemostaic, Abscess.
<i>Nitraria retusa</i>	Shoots, Leaves	Dermatitis, Abscess, Acne.
<i>Olea europaea</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Gingivitis, Dyspepsia, Eczema, Constipation, Earache.
<i>Periploca angustifolia</i>	Shoots	Anguish.
<i>Phillyrea angustifolia</i>	Leaves	Gingivitis, Hypertension.
<i>Phlomis floccosa</i>	Leaves	Metritis.
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	Cones	Liver diseases, respiratory diseases.
<i>Pistachia lentiscus</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Colic, Gastritis, Skin cracks, Ulcer, Gingivitis, Psoriasis, Dermatitis, Rash, Piles, Colitis, Cracks of hands and feet.
<i>Quercus coccifera</i>	Bark, fruits, Leaves	Enuresis, Metritis, Gingivitis, Dermatitis, Diarrhea, Vaginal diseases, Prostatitis, Cough, Hypertension, Ulcer, Cystitis, Vaginitis.
<i>Retama raetam</i>	Shoots	Diabetes, Sinusitis.
<i>Rhamnus lycioides</i>	Shoots, Leaves	Vitiligo.
<i>Rhus tripartita</i>	Bark, Fruits, Leaves	Gastritis, Toothache, Ulcer, Piles, Eczema, Cracks of hands and feet, Cystitis, Athlete's foot.
<i>Ricinus communis</i>	Leaves, Seeds	Chest allergy, Hair-fall, Constipation, Cough, Colic, Common cold, Abscess, Headache, Rheumatic, Arthritis, Contraceptive.

<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Shoots, Leaves	Headache, Rheumatic, Flatulence, Womb and stomach tumors, Memory loss, Menstruation, strengthen blood vessels, Tranquilizing for nerves, Liver diseases, Gallbladder stones, Dizziness.
<i>Rubus sanctus</i>	Leaves	Gingivitis, Diarrhea, Colic.
<i>Sacropoterium spinosum</i>	Roots	Piles, Gastritis.
<i>Salix subserrata</i>	Leaves	Anticancer, Fever, Diabetes, Enuresis.
<i>Smliax aspera</i>	Leaves, Fruits	Dermatitis, Blood purification.
<i>Spartium junceum</i>	Shoots	Laxative.
<i>Suaeda vera</i>	Shoots	Scabies, Herpes.
<i>Tamarix arborea</i>	Shoots, Bark	Diarrhea, Indigestion.
<i>Thymelaea hirsuta</i>	Leaves, Shoots	Hair-fall, Vermicide, Warts, Herpes, Dermatitis.
<i>Viburnum tinus</i>	Shoots, Leaves	Gastritis, Dropsy.
<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Leaves	Vermicide, Diuretic.
<i>Ziziphus lotus</i>	Leaves, Fruit, Roots, Bark	Constipation, Hair parasites, Gastritis, Sciatica, Abscess, Piles, Hepatitis.
<i>Zygophyllum album</i>	Leaves	Diabetes, Hypertension.

DISCUSSION

In this study it is difficult to state which plants are most economically important to the inhabitants of the regions. As Grenad has noted, the term "useful species" does not have the same meaning for all cultures and probably not for all individuals within a society [15]. In fact, the inhabitants of Eastern region stated that not all the plants in the area are useful. In consistence with this, more than 20 species of the recorded species in the area were not mentioned by them to have any economic value. We are precisely unable to explain this point, but one may suggest that this may be ascribed to the lack of awareness of the inhabitants for the economic values of these species, or it may be due to inexperienced trials in ailment treatment [16].

As a final point, the sustainable management of Eastern region resources and the importance of its medicinal plants definitely propose advantages to the present generation and to meet the needs and aspirations of futures generations. Conservation activities involving medicinal plant gardens maintained by herbalists, herbaria and various arboreta are necessary. Specials programs must be started and utilized all the conventional methods of conservation (in situ and ex situ conservation, gene banks, biotechnology, etc.). Education of the rural dwellers, particularly the herbalists and the herb sellers in conservation awareness is important for an effective approach to the sustainable utilization of the natural resources in the region. [17,18].

The flora of Libya still needs extensive studies as it is far from being fairly known. Both floristic and monographic studies should go parallel to each other in order to achieve a reasonable level of knowledge of that flora within a reasonable time. The wild trees and shrubs in Eastern region of Libya suffered extreme degradation mainly through the mismanagement by the people making fire wood, excessive grazing, cutting of trees and shrubs for charcoal and brushwood, clearing the vegetation for cultivating the ground to be abandoned later (what is known as shifting cultivation) is carried out in many parts of the area, drought hazards, diseases, insect and lichens. Similarly, Awada noted that [19]. As a result of these factors, many species as *Arbutus pavarii*, *Quercus coccifera*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Laurus nobilis*, *Myrtus communis*, *Phillyrea angustifolia*, *Rhus tripartite* have become threatened by extinction. There is urgent need for international assistance to collect the endangered plants and to conserve the genetic resources.

CONCLUSION

Considering that the Eastern region of Libya has a high diversity of medicinal plants that are still poorly studied, more phytochemical and pharmacological studies are necessary in order to test popular indications and search for new pharmaceuticals. Additional studies are also necessary to identify possible links between a plant's chemical composition and its habitat and life strategy and to determine how human populations Eastern region select and use plants.

Participation of public and private associations in management and utilization of medicinal plants in sustainable approach is indispensable to contest human pressures on these valuable natural resources.

Disclaimer

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Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

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